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A TECHNICAL REPORT ON THE ANALYSIS, COMPARISON, AND
SELECTION OF MOTORS AND MOTOR DRIVERS FOR THE MOTION
SYSTEM DESIGN OF A FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION (FFF) 3D
PRINTER

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the research work, **"THE ANALYSIS, COMPARISON, AND SELECTION OF MOTORS AND MOTOR DRIVERS FOR THE MOTION SYSTEM DESIGN OF A FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION (FFF) 3D PRINTER"** was done by Obidike Nzubechukwu Ifeanyichukwu in fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the Bachelor of Engineering degree in Mechatronics Engineering, Federal University of Technology Owerri.

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DEDICATION

This report is dedicated to the Almighty God for his faithfulness and help throughout my entire academic journey and during this research. I am also thankful to my professors, instructors, mentors and individuals whose unwavering support, encouragement, and inspiration have been the driving force behind its completion and for training me with what is needed to succeed in engineering discipline. To my family, whose boundless love and understanding have been the foundation throughout this journey. Finally, to all those whose belief in the power of knowledge and exploration continues to shape my aspirations and inspire me to keep striving for the ultimate excellence.

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ABSTRACT

This report presents the design and evaluation of the drive system for a 3D printer, with a focus on the motor and motor driver components of the 3D printer which is used in 3D printing also referred to as **additive manufacturing**. The drive system plays a critical role in the performance and precision of 3D printers. Stepper motors, specifically the **NEMA 17 model**, were selected for their accuracy and cost-effectiveness. To control these motors, **A4988, DRV8825 and TMC series** motor drivers were examined. The **TMC drivers** were found to offer superior noise reduction and smoother motion compared to the **A4988**. The report also detailed the design methodology/materials & method, literature review, and rationale for selecting motors and motor drivers, their integration into the printer's control system, and the testing of motor performance parameters such as torque, speed, and noise, with a focus on future innovation. The findings emphasize the importance of choosing the right motor and driver for enhancing print quality and efficiency.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of 3D Printing Technology:

The advancement of 3D printing technology has transformed various industries, enabling rapid prototyping, complex geometrical constructions, and customized production across sectors from automotive, healthcare, aerospace, education to consumer goods. A vital component of this technology is the drive system (motors and motor driver), which governs the precise movement of the print head and the print bed, thereby facilitating the layer-by-layer assembly of materials. The performance of a 3D printer largely depends on the accuracy, reliability, and efficiency of its motors and motor drivers. These components directly control the precision of the printed object, affecting the overall quality of the output (Printed material). This report aims to explore the function, design, and selection criteria for motors and motor drivers within the context of a 3D printer's drive system, focusing on their importance in ensuring smooth and accurate printing operations. It also highlights recent advancements in motor and driver technologies, which have contributed to better print quality, quieter operation, and increased reliability.

Figure 1.0: 3D Printer (www.techradar.com/3d-printers)

1.2 Importance of Motors and Motor Drivers:

At the heart of the 3D printer's drive system are the motors and motor drivers. These components are responsible for controlling the movement of the printer head and the print bed in either (x, y or z axis) direction. Motors translate electrical signals (digital signal) into mechanical motion, while motor drivers regulate the power supplied to the motors, ensuring smooth and accurate movement they act as power modulators to the system.

The design and implementation of motors and motor drivers are pivotal in determining the overall performance of the 3D printer. Advances in these technologies have led to improvements in speed, torque, accuracy, and reliability. Modern motors can achieve high resolutions and precise movements, while sophisticated motor drivers enhance the efficiency and stability of these operations.

1.3 Motors and Motor Drivers Used in 3D Printers

1.3.1 Motors

1.3.1.1 Stepper Motors:

- **NEMA 17 Stepper Motors:** They are the most used in 3D printers due to their balance of torque, precision, and affordability.
- **NEMA 23 Stepper Motors:** They can be used for applications requiring more torque and power, but they are less common in standard desktop 3D printers.

Figure 1.1: Stepper Motor(<https://www.orientalmotor.com/steppermotors/technology/step>)

1.3.1.2 Servo Motors:

- The servo motors are not commonly used as stepper motors in 3D printers, because they are generally expensive and too complex to control.

Figure 1.2: Servo Motor (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/servomotor>)

1.3.2 Motor Drivers

- **A4988 Stepper Motor Drivers:** They are affordable and widely used but can generate more heat and noise when compared to more advanced drivers, it's cons which is the generation of excessive heat and noise which is a huge consideration in the design of a 3D printer is a drawback for this type of motor driver.

Figure 1.3: A4988 Stepper Motor Driver (www.JSumo.com)

- **DRV8825 Stepper Motor Drivers:** They offer higher current output than the A4988 motor drivers and has better heat dissipation, making it a popular choice.

© Photo by Electronics

Figure 1.4: DRV8825 Stepper Motor Driver (www.JSumo.com)

- **Trinamic Series (TMC2100, TMC2130, TMC2208, etc.):** The trinamic series are known for their quiet operations and smooth motion. They offer features like Stall detection and higher micro-stepping capabilities, which makes them to be highly sort after when designing a 3D printer.

Figure 1.5: Trinamic Series Stepper Motor Drivers (www.JSumo.com)

1.4 Schematic of a 3D Printer Drive System

Figure 1.6: Schematic of a 3D Printer Drive System

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Motors in 3D Printing

2.11 Stepper Motors:

Stepper motors also known as **step motors** or **stepping motors**, are brushless DC electric motors that rotates in a series of small and discrete angular steps (Escudier & Atkins, 2019). They are the most widely used motors in 3D printers due to their ability to offer precise control over motion without requiring a feedback system such as an encoder or sensor. This is possible because stepper motors operate by moving in discrete steps, which allows for accurate positioning and control based on the number of steps taken. Each step corresponds to a specific rotational movement, making it possible to predict and control the motor's position precisely without the need for continuous feedback.

This open-loop control system makes stepper motors simpler and more cost-effective, which is why they are popular in applications like 3D printing, where precise movement is essential.

Stepper motors can be effectively controlled without requiring complicated configurations (V, R, S, & R, 2024). This control is crucial in applications where accuracy and repeatability are essential, such as 3D printing which is also referred to as additive manufacturing. Stepper motors operate in discrete steps, which can be finely controlled by micro-stepping technique to provide smooth motion and higher resolution in movement. The micro-stepping control system also improves the positioning accuracy and eliminates low speed ripple and resonance effects in a stepper motor electrical drive (K & A, 2023). They also deliver high torque at low speeds, a critical requirement in the design and operation of 3D printers.

- Stepper motors typically require **DC (Direct Current)** for their operation. They are designed to work with a DC power supply, which provides the

necessary current to the motor windings to create the magnetic fields that drive the motor's rotation (Fiore, 2021). The **DC** is then converted into timed pulses that energize the motor windings in a specific sequence to control the motor's steps.

However, **AC (Alternating Current) stepper motors** also exist, but they are less common and operate differently. These are more typically found in specialized industrial applications.

In most 3D printing and other applications, **DC stepper motors** are used because they offer better control over positioning and are easier to interface with the common electronic drivers, such as A4988, DRV8825, and TMC2208, which also rely on **DC** input.

Figure 2.0: Stepper Motor (<https://images.app.goo>.

gl/Wmk2S5KfLUNbKPkKA)

2.11.1 Recent Developments in Stepper Motor Technology for 3D Printers

In recent years, advancements in stepper motor technology have further solidified their role in 3D printing. Hybrid stepper motors, for instance have been developed to combine the features of variable reluctance and permanent magnet stepper motors, providing better torque control and reducing resonance issues that were common in earlier designs (Mohammadreza Hojati & Soury, 2022). These motors are highly efficient in low-speed applications, which is typically required for most desktop 3D printer.

2.11.2 Types of Stepper Motor

There are three primary types of stepper motors:

1. **Permanent Magnet (PM) Stepper Motors:** Permanent magnet stepper motors use a permanent magnet rotor and are known for their high torque at low speeds. The rotor aligns with the stator's magnetic field, which moves in steps as the current in the coil's changes. While they provide decent precision, their step angles are generally larger, and they are less common in applications requiring high accuracy, like 3D printing. The Step angles of a permanent magnet stepper motor ranges from **7.5° to 15° (48 – 24 steps/revolution)** (motioncontrolproducts, 2022). They offer lower resolution compared to other types. Permanent magnet motors are designed for applications that don't require extreme precision.
2. **Variable Reluctance (VR) Stepper Motors:** In variable reluctance stepper motors, the rotor is made of a soft iron and lacks any magnetization. The motor operates by minimizing the reluctance (magnetic resistance) between the rotor and stator. These motors are known for having small step angles, but they typically provide less torque than permanent magnet and

hybrid stepper motors. The Step angles of a VR stepper motor are usually 5° to 15° , but with improvements in design, some motors can achieve smaller step angles of around 1.8° . VR stepper motors are often less common in applications that require high torque.

3. **Hybrid Stepper Motors:** Hybrid stepper motors combine the features of both permanent magnet and variable reluctance stepper motors designs to provide better performance (Faradyi, 2023). They have a magnetized rotor like PM motors, but also feature fine-toothed rotors and stators, like VR motors. This combination allows for smaller step angles (e.g., 1.8° or even finer) and higher torque, making hybrid stepper motors the most precise and efficient type of stepper motor. These motors have the smallest step angles, typically **1.8° per step** (200 steps per revolution) and can go as low as **0.9°** (400 steps per revolution) with finer control through micro-stepping. The hybrid design offers the highest precision and smoothness, which makes it suitable for use in designing a 3D printer. A typical example of the hybrid stepper motor used in the design of a 3D printer is the NEMA series.

Figure 2.1: Hybrid Stepper Motor

(<https://www.linengineering.com/technology/hybrid-stepper-motors>)

Figure 2.2: Torque-speed relationship of a Stepper Motor
 (<https://www.exro.com/industry-insights/torque-and-speed-relationship-the-fundamental-challenge-of-e-mobility>)

2.11.3 NEMA Series

The **NEMA** series refers to a set of standards developed by the “**National Electrical Manufacturers Association**”, specifying the mounting and physical dimensions of stepper motors. Among the various **NEMA** sizes, **NEMA 17** and **NEMA 23** are commonly used in 3D printers. **NEMA 17** is the most popular due to its balance of size, torque, and precision.

- **NEMA 17** hybrid stepper motors are widely used in 3D printers for both the extruder and the axes movements (**X**, **Y**, and **Z**). Their precise control, especially when paired with micro-stepping drivers, ensures accurate positioning of the print head and build platform, leading to high-quality prints. The **1.8°** step angle (200 steps per revolution) typical of **NEMA 17** motors offers the right balance of resolution and torque, enabling smooth motion and minimizing the risk of skipped steps, which could ruin a print. Additionally, the torque-to-size ratio of **NEMA 17** hybrid stepper motors

is ideal for handling the relatively low weight of 3D printer components while providing enough force to move the extruder and bed without loss of precision.

Overall, the use of NEMA series hybrid stepper motors, particularly NEMA 17, is central to achieving the high precision, reliability, and repeatability required in 3D printing.

2.11.4 Advantages of Stepper Motor

- Precise positioning over full or part rotation with high resolution.
- Excellent speed and position control in open loop systems without feedback devices.
- Ability to start, stop and operate at constant angular velocity with high degree of precision.
- Hold their position efficiently without power due to highly detented nature.
- Easy control using pulses which makes programming simpler.
- Less maintenance required as there are no brushes.

2.11.5 Disadvantages of Stepper Motor

- Vibration and resonance are likely if not designed properly.
- Require driver circuit to function properly which increases cost.
- Less accurate at high speeds due to delay between pulses.

2.12 Servo Motors:

A servomotor (or **servo motor** or simply **servo**) (Escudier & Atkins, 2019) is a rotary actuator that allows for precise control of angular position, It consists of a motor coupled to a sensor for position feedback It also requires a servo drive to complete the system, the drive uses the feedback sensor to precisely control the rotary position of the motor (kollmorgen, 2024). Unlike open-loop systems such as stepper motors, servo motors operate in a **closed-loop system**, meaning they use real-time feedback mechanisms to continuously monitor and adjust their

position. This feedback is provided by sensors such as encoders, which allow the servo motor to detect and correct any deviations in motion, ensuring **high precision and accuracy**.

In the context of 3D printing, servo motors offer **smooth operation** with excellent torque control, even at high speeds. This makes them suitable for **high-end 3D printers** where precision and repeatability are crucial. They are also known for being energy-efficient, as they consume power proportionally to the load, they are handling, leading to less heat generation and better overall performance during long print jobs.

Servo motors can also provide high torque at both low and high speeds, making them ideal for **large-format 3D printers** or industrial machines that require robust mechanical systems. They are often used in applications where **fine detailing** and **high resolution** are necessary, such as in aerospace, automotive, and medical device manufacturing. The **servo motors** are not commonly used in comparison to **stepper motors** in **3D printers**, because they are generally **expensive and too complex to control**.

- Servo motors typically requires both **DC (Direct Current)** and **AC (Alternating Current)** for operation, depending on their design and application.

DC Servo Motors:

DC servo motors are commonly used in applications requiring precise control of position, speed, and torque. They consist of a small DC motor, position sensing device, feedback circuit, gear system, and a control circuit¹. These motors are known for their high starting torque and quick response to control signals (Saini, 2022).

AC Servo Motors:

AC servo motors, on the other hand, are typically used in applications where high efficiency and high-power output are required. They operate on AC power and are often used in industrial applications such as **industrial 3D printing**, robotics, CNC machinery, and automation systems. AC servo

Figure 2.3: Labelled Servo Motor Diagram

([https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/servo motor](https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/servo-motor))

Figure 2.4: Torque-speed relationship of a Servo Motor

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/servo>)

motor)

2.12.1 Advantages of Servo Motors

1. **High Precision and Accuracy:** Servo motors use a closed-loop feedback system, allowing them to adjust and correct their position in real time, making them highly accurate.
2. **High Torque at All Speeds:** Servo motors maintain consistent torque even at high speeds, making them ideal for applications that require both power and speed.
3. **Energy Efficient:** They draw only the necessary amount of power based on the load, leading to reduced heat generation and lower power consumption.
4. **Smooth Operation:** Due to the continuous feedback and fine control, servo motors provide smooth motion without the risk of skipped steps, which is common in stepper motors.
5. **Dynamic Performance:** They offer excellent acceleration and deceleration, making them suitable for applications requiring rapid changes in movement.

2.12.2 Disadvantages of Servo Motors

1. **Higher Cost:** Servo motors are more expensive than stepper motors due to their complex design and additional components, such as encoders.
2. **Complexity in Setup:** Implementing a servo motor requires advanced control systems and more components, making it harder to install and maintain.
3. **Feedback Dependency:** Since they rely on encoders for feedback, any malfunction in the feedback system can lead to performance issues.

4. **Requires Tuning:** Servo motors often need to be tuned for optimal performance, which can be time-consuming and requires technical knowledge.

2.13 Key Difference between Stepper Motor and Servo Motor

1. Control and Accuracy:

- **Servo Motors:** Servo motors use a closed-loop control system, meaning they continuously receive feedback from encoders to adjust their position. This allows for precise control and the ability to correct any positional errors. In 3D printers, this enables the motor to achieve higher accuracy and smoother motion, which is especially important for high-end, professional printers where fine detail and layer precision are critical.
- **Stepper Motors:** Stepper motors, in contrast, operate on an open-loop system. They move in fixed increments (steps) without feedback, making them less precise than servos. They can miss steps under heavy loads or high speeds without the ability to self-correct, which can affect print quality, particularly on complex designs.

2. Torque and Speed:

- **Servo Motors:** Servo motors excel in delivering high torque at both high and low speeds, maintaining smooth movement even under load. This makes them ideal for high-speed 3D printing applications without sacrificing quality. Moreover, they can operate more efficiently, adjusting their torque based on the required load.
- **Stepper Motors:** Stepper motors offer high torque at low speeds but their performance declines significantly as speed increases. At higher speeds, they tend to lose torque, which can limit the speed of printing or reduce the consistency in layer deposition.

3. Efficiency and Power Consumption:

- **Servo Motors:** Servo motors are typically more efficient because they draw only the power required to maintain torque based on real-time feedback. This allows for better energy management, especially in prolonged print jobs on industrial printers. Additionally, servo motors produce less heat and consume less power over time compared to stepper motors.
- **Stepper Motors:** Stepper motors tend to draw constant current regardless of load, making them less energy efficient. They can overheat more easily during long print cycles, affecting their longevity and performance, the use of sink can account for this.

4. Feedback Mechanism:

- **Servo Motors:** The primary advantage of servo motors is their feedback loop, which constantly monitors the motor's position and speed using encoders. This feedback ensures precise movement and makes the motor resistant to overshooting or missing steps, even under varying conditions such as changes in load or acceleration.
- **Stepper Motors:** Stepper motors lack a feedback mechanism and thus have no way of detecting if they have missed a step. This can lead to cumulative errors, especially in long or complex print jobs, where small inaccuracies build up over time.

5. Cost and Complexity:

- **Servo Motors:** Servo motors tend to be more expensive and complex to implement. They require additional components like encoders, and their control systems are more sophisticated. As a result, they are typically found in **high-end, industrial-grade 3D printers** where the investment is justified by the higher level of precision and reliability.

- **Stepper Motors:** Stepper motors are generally less expensive and simpler to integrate into 3D printers, making them a popular choice for **entry-level to mid-range 3D printers**. Their lower cost and simpler control systems make them ideal for budget-conscious applications where extreme precision is not a top priority.

2.2 Motor Drivers in 3D Printing:

Motor drivers are crucial components in 3D printers, responsible for controlling the motors that drive the machine's mechanical movements. They serve as an interface between the microcontroller and the motors, converting low-power signals from the controller into the high-power signals needed to operate the motors, they function as power modulators. Their primary roles include regulating current, voltage, and managing the step sequencing of stepper motors, ensuring smooth and precise movements necessary for accurate 3D printing (O'Connell, 2021)[10] (McCollum, 2023).

Motor drivers also provide features like current limiting, overheat protection, and micro-stepping, which helps control motor speed and position more precisely (McCollum, 2023). This makes them essential for controlling the motion of the print head and build platform, directly influencing the print's resolution and quality (Rob, 2023).

Figure 2.5: Motor Driver(google.com)

2.21 Basic Functionality:

1. **Current Control:** Motor drivers adjust the amount of current supplied to the motor, which is crucial for ensuring optimal torque and preventing overheating. By regulating the current, motor drivers maintain the motor's performance without overloading it.
2. **Voltage Control:** Motor drivers step down or step up the voltage supplied to the motor, ensuring that it operates within its required voltage range. This is critical for protecting the motor from damage due to voltage fluctuations.
3. **Step Sequencing:** For stepper motors, motor drivers control the step sequence by sending timed electrical pulses to the motor's coils, enabling precise movement. This ensures accurate control over the position, speed, and torque of the motor, which is essential for achieving high precision in 3D printing. Advanced drivers can perform micro-stepping, which divides each step into smaller increments for higher resolution and smoother movements.

2.22 Popular Motor Drivers in 3D Printing

Several motor drivers are commonly used in 3D printers, each with unique features that make them suited for different needs. Here are some of the most popular:

1. A4988 Motor Driver:

- The **A4988**, developed by Allegro Microsystems is a widely used, cost-effective motor driver, known for its micro-stepping capabilities (up to **16 micro-steps**).
- It allows for current limiting and over-temperature protection, making it versatile and durable for controlling small to medium stepper motors.

- While it's affordable, the **A4988** is not ideal for silent operations, as it tends to generate some noise when the motor operates at higher speeds ([Richter, 2018](#)).

2. DRV8825 Motor Driver:

- The **DRV8825**, developed by Texas Instruments is a step up from the **A4988**, offering up to **32 micro-steps** for smoother motor control and greater precision.
- It can handle higher current (up to **2.2A** per coil), making it suitable for driving larger motors with more torque.
- Like the **A4988**, it supports thermal shutdown and overcurrent protection, but it is also louder compared to more modern drivers. However, it may have issues with accurate micro-stepping ([Richter, 2018](#)).

3. TMC2208 Motor Driver:

- The **TMC2208** developed by Trinamic Motion Control is a newer generation motor driver that is popular for its silent step technology. This driver operates in Stealth-Chop mode, reducing motor noise to near-silent levels, making it ideal for 3D printers operating in quieter environments. The **TMC2208** motor driver offers up to **256 micro-steps** for smoother motor control and greater precision as stated in the datasheet ([KG, 2017](#)).
- It supports smooth motion and current regulation, improving both the performance and lifespan of the motors.
- The **TMC2208** is also known for being easy to configure and offers automatic mode switching between Stealth-Chop (silent) and Spread-Cycle (high-performance) modes depending on load

requirements. This driver is particularly popular in high-end 3D printers (O'Connell, 2021)[11].

Figure 2.6: TMC2208 Basic Block Diagram
 (<https://www.analog.com/en/products/tmc2208.html>)

2.23 Why TMC2208 Motor Drivers is the Best Fit for NEMA 17 Motors in 3D Printing:

The **TMC2208** motor driver is often considered the best fit for **NEMA 17** stepper motors, which are commonly used in 3D printers, for the following reasons:

1. **Silent Operation:** The Stealth-Chop technology in the **TMC2208** ensures that the motors operate almost silently, making the printer much quieter during operation (O'Connell, 2021). This is a significant advantage in 3D printing, particularly in home or office environments where noise can be disruptive.
2. **High Precision:** The **TMC2208** offers micro-stepping up to 256 micro-steps, allowing for extremely fine control of the motor. This results in smoother movements and higher accuracy, which is crucial for producing detailed and high-quality 3D prints (O'Connell, 2021).
3. **Energy Efficiency:** The driver adjusts the current dynamically based on the load, making it more energy-efficient than older drivers like the **A4988**

or **DRV8825**. This reduces power consumption and prevents excessive heat buildup during long printing jobs.

4. **Low Heat Generation:** The **TMC2208** operates efficiently, generating less heat compared to older motor drivers. This extends the lifespan of both the driver and the motor, making it ideal for extended 3D printing tasks ([Electronics, 2024](#)).
5. **Compatibility with NEMA 17:** NEMA 17 stepper motors, commonly used in 3D printers, are perfectly matched with the **TMC2208** in terms of voltage, current handling, compact size and high torque ([John, 2023](#)). This ensures that the motor performs optimally without overheating or losing steps, even during high-torque operations.

TMC2208 motor drivers is the best fit for **NEMA 17** motors in 3D printing due to its silent operation, high precision, energy efficiency, and smooth performance. Its modern features make it the preferred choice for the design of 3D printers where both quality and user experience are critical.

2.24 Challenges and Limitations of Current Motors and Motor Drivers Design

1. Cost:

- High-end motors and motor drivers with advanced features like silent operation (e.g., TMC2208) or precision control (e.g., servo motors) come at a significantly higher cost. This can limit their accessibility in low-cost or DIY 3D printers. For example, servo motors are generally more expensive than stepper motors due to their closed-loop systems and feedback mechanisms, making them less common in hobbyist applications.

2. Energy Consumption:

- While motor drivers like the **TMC2208** are designed to be energy efficient, many traditional motor designs, especially in industrial applications, still consume high amounts of energy. Stepper motors, for instance, draw constant current even when idle, which results in inefficient power use compared to other motor types, such as servo motors, which only consume power based on the load.

3. Heat Generation:

- Stepper motors and their drivers, especially those like the **A4988** or **DRV8825**, can generate significant heat when driving motors at higher current settings. Excessive heat not only reduces efficiency but can also cause thermal shutdowns, wear out components faster, and impact the longevity of the motor and driver. To counter this, cooling mechanisms are often needed, adding complexity and cost to the design.

4. Precision Limits at Higher Speeds:

- At higher speeds, stepper motors lose precision due to missed steps and reduced torque. While micro-stepping helps to improve accuracy at low speeds, maintaining that same level of precision becomes challenging as speed increases. In comparison, servo motors maintain precision at high speeds, but this comes with a trade-off in terms of cost and complexity.

5. Noise and Vibration:

- Standard stepper motors tend to produce noise and vibration, especially at higher speeds. While advanced drivers like the **TMC2208** address this with features like Stealth-Chop for silent

operation, cheaper drivers such as the **A4988** or **DRV8825** still produce noticeable noise, which can be undesirable in applications requiring quiet operation.

6. Torque and Load Handling:

- Stepper motors can deliver high torque at low speeds but suffer from reduced torque as speed increases. This limitation can be problematic in 3D printers that need to move heavy print heads or extruders at high speeds. Servo motors outperform stepper motors in this area but come at a higher cost, making them less appealing for cost-sensitive projects.

7. Driver Complexity:

- Advanced motor drivers, particularly servo motor drivers, require complex tuning and calibration for optimal performance. This increases the setup time and technical knowledge needed to implement them effectively. Additionally, the closed-loop feedback system of servo motors requires more components (such as encoders), adding to the system's overall complexity.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY/MATERIALS & METHODS

3.1 Design Selection Criteria

3.11 Motor Type Selection:

For the 3D printer design, **NEMA 17** stepper motors were chosen due to their high precision, torque capabilities, and cost-effectiveness. Stepper motors offer open-loop control, meaning they operate by counting the steps for precise movements without needing feedback sensors, which reduces complexity and cost (Dietrich, 2022).

- **Precision:** The typical step angle of **1.8°** per step precision allows for fine control over positioning, which is crucial in 3D printing for accurate layer deposition. This ensures that **NEMA 17** can handle the weight of the print bed and extruder, preventing misalignment during printing tasks which is crucial for high-quality prints.
- **Torque:** Additionally, the **NEMA 17** stepper motor was selected because of its optimal balance between size and torque, delivering sufficient holding torque (around **45 Ncm**) and Precision (**1.8°** per step) for the 3D printer's requirements as stated in the datasheet (Component101, 2019).
- **Cost and Availability:** Stepper motors are cost-effective and widely available, making them an ideal choice for this 3D printer design.

3.12 Motor Driver Selection:

The motor driver chosen for the 3D printer is the **TMC2208 stepper motor driver**. This driver was selected based on several important considerations:

- **Current Rating:** The **TMC2208** current rating of up to (**2A per coil**), is well-suited to drive the **NEMA 17** stepper motor at optimal performance (KG, 2017).

- **Stealth-Chop Mode:** The **TMC2208** incorporates **Stealth-Chop technology**, which ensures ultra-quiet motor operation, significantly reducing the noise produced by the printer during operation. This is a key advantage for 3D printers designed for home or office use (KG, 2017).
- **Micro-stepping:** The **TMC2208** supports up to **1/256 micro-stepping**, enabling smoother motion and improved precision over traditional drivers with fewer micro-stepping levels (KG, 2017).
- **Ease of Integration:** The **TMC2208** is compatible with most standard control boards and firmware used in 3D printers, such as **Marlin**, making it a seamless option for this design.

3.2 Design Analysis

3.2.1 Load and Torque Calculation:

To ensure the selected motor could handle the necessary load, calculations were performed based on the mechanical requirements of the 3D printer.

- **Load Calculation:** The print head assembly weighs **X kg**, and the maximum acceleration required for printing tasks is **X m/s²**. Using Newton's second law:

$$F = ma = \text{mass} * \text{acceleration} = \text{X newton}$$

- **Torque Calculation:** With a pulley radius of **x meters**, the torque required is:

$$T = F * r = \text{force} * \text{radius} = \text{X newton meter}$$

3.22 Driver Circuitry Design:

The TMC2208 driver circuitry includes features such as current regulation and thermal protection, ensuring optimal motor performance.

- **Current Limiting:** The TMC2208 allows for precise control of current through **UART (Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter) programming** which is a protocol used for serial communication. It is a physical circuit in a microcontroller or a stand-alone IC. The main purpose of a **UART** is to transmit and receive serial data. This ensures that the motor receives the correct amount of current without overheating.
- **Stealth-Chop Operation:** The TMC2208 operates in Stealth-Chop mode for silent operation at low speeds and Spread-Cycle mode at higher speeds for consistent torque output (KG, 2017).
- **Signal Input Methods:** The driver receives signals from the 3D printer's control board, typically using a microcontroller like the ATmega2560. The microcontroller sends pulse signals to the driver, controlling the motor's speed and direction.

The **TMC2208** motor driver is known for its silent step technology and low noise operation. It uses an **H-Bridge circuit** to control current through the stepper motor coils, allowing precise micro-stepping for smooth motion. The driver integrates current-limiting functionality that automatically adjusts motor current based on the load, optimizing performance and reducing power consumption. Additionally, it features **UART** communication, enabling real-time adjustment of motor parameters such as **speed** and **torque**. Voltage regulation ensures consistent power delivery to prevent motor stalling or overheating.

This makes the **TMC2208** an excellent choice for **NEMA 17** motors in 3D printing applications, as it improves efficiency and reduces heat dissipation.

Figure 3.0: TMC2208 Elaborate Block Diagram
<https://www.analog.com/en/products/tmc2208.html>

3.3 Software Implementation

3.31 Firmware and Motor Control Algorithm:

The TMC2208 motor driver interfaces seamlessly with Marlin firmware, which is widely used in 3D printers. Key features of this implementation include:

- **Micro-stepping Control:** Marlin firmware can dynamically adjust the micro-stepping resolution of the TMC2208, allowing up to **1/256 micro-steps** for highly smooth motion control (KG, 2017).
- **UART Communication:** The TMC2208 supports **UART** communication with the control board, enabling advanced configuration of motor parameters such as current limits and operating modes through software (KG, 2017).

Figure 3.1: UART Communication in TMC2208 Motor Driver

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APPENDIX

Table 3.0: Bill of Engineering Material and Evaluation

S/N	Material	Specification	Quantity	Unit cost (#)	Total cost (#)
1	Stepper Motors	Nema 17	4	16,300	65,200
2	Stepper Motor Driver	TMC 2208	4	3,075	12,300
3	Motor Bracket		4	3,000	12,000
				Total	89,500